

Fine-scale temperature variability creates distinct thermal environments within a coral reef atoll

Grimaldi et al., 2022; *Coral Reefs*

General information

Title of dataset	Fine-scale temperature variability creates distinct thermal environments within a coral reef atoll
URL of dataset	10.5281/zenodo.6999217
Abstract	This study investigates the complex thermal environments across a coral reef atoll using fine-scale temperature measurements.
Keywords	Coral reef, Temperature, Atoll, Hydrodynamics, Reef Zones, Northwestern Australia
Lead author for the dataset	Camille Grimaldi
Title and position of lead author	Dr., Post-doctoral Research Associate
Organization and address of lead author	UWA Oceans Institute and Ocean Graduate School The University of Western Australia, M004 35 Stirling Highway, Crawley, WA, 6009
Email address of lead author	camille.grimaldi@uwa.edu.au
Additional authors or contributors to the dataset	R. J. Lowe, J. A. Benthuisen, M. V. W. Cuttler, R. H. Green, J. P. Gilmour
Organization associated with the data	University of Western Australia
License	This data is publicly available and free to use.
Geographic location – verbal	Mermaid Reef off the North West Shelf of Australia.

description	
Temporal coverage	November 2017 – October 2018
Methods description	Please refer to the methods description in the manuscript.

Description of files included in the dataset:

Dataset filename	Dataset description
RawTemperatures.mat	mat-file with the raw temperature data conditions (November 2017 – October 2018): date (datetime format) and temperature (in °C) from HOBO Temperature loggers
SiteLocation.txt	txt-file with the site coordinates. Variables: site =site name; lon= longitude in degrees East; lat = latitude in degrees North